

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF NICKEL FERROCYANIDE COMPLEX

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The formation and precipitation of nickel ferrocyanide has been studied by potentiometric titrations between nickel sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide using ferri-ferrocyanide electrode both by the direct and the inverse methods. The point of inflection obtained from the maximum value of $\Delta E/\Delta C$ corresponds to the formation of a double salt having the composition $4Ni_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3K_4Fe(CN)_6$, with either of the substances used as the reagent. The potentiometric curves have a regular shape: a sharp break in potential occurs at the equivalence point and the titration results are accurate and reproducible. The effect of alcohol on the end-point as well as on the nature of curves has been studied.

The reaction between nickel salts and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ has been investigated by several workers by purely analytical methods and also by physico-chemical methods, but there is hardly any co-ordination of the views expressed by them. Werner (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1919, 58, 23) reported the quantitative precipitation of a bluish green compound $Ni_2Fe(CN)_6$. Treadwell and Chervet (*Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1922, 5, 633) suggested the composition as $K_2NiFe(CN)_6$. Gasper *et al.* (*Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1926, 24, 323) reported that the nickel ferrocyanide was possibly a double, complex or associated salt. Rene Paris (*Compt. rend.*, 1934, 199, 863) showed that the composition of nickel ferrocyanide was between $K_2NiFe(CN)_6$ and $Ni_4K_4[Fe(CN)_6]_2$. Velculescu (*Bull. Chim. Soc. Romania*, 1933, 34, 471) reported that ferrocyanide of nickel was not a pure compound but probably a mixture of $3K_2NiFe(CN)_6$ and $Ni_2Fe(CN)_6$. Wyrubow (*Annalen*, 8, 444) observed that the composition of the precipitate changed from $K_2NiFe(CN)_6$ to $K_2Ni_3[Fe(CN)_6]_2$ on addition of excess of ferrocyanide. Tananaev and Levina (*Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1946, 1, 224) studied the reaction between $NiSO_4$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ electrolytically, colorimetrically and turbidimetrically and showed that the reaction proceeded in three stages: $Ni_2Fe(CN)_6$, $Ni_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2K_4Fe(CN)_6$, and in the third phase, a double salt $2Ni_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot K_4Fe(CN)_6$ was formed. With $Na_4Fe(CN)_6$ the precipitate had the composition $Na_2Ni_3[Fe(CN)_6]_2$ and with $Li_4Fe(CN)_6$, $Ni_2Fe(CN)_6$ was quantitatively precipitated.

In view of the conflicting opinions and in the absence of any decisive views on the composition of nickel ferrocyanide, it was considered worthwhile to make its detailed study by physico-chemical methods to obtain more conclusive evidences on the composition of complex metallic ferro- and ferricyanides (Saxena *et al.*, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1956, 285, 90; 1954, 276, 204; this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 141, 222, 703; 1952, 29, 263, 284, 529, 535; 1954, 31, 53, 56, 157 etc.). In this paper only the results of potentiometric titrations have been included and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Merck's guaranteed extrapure reagents [$NiSO_4$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$] were used. The strengths of the solutions were estimated by standard methods of analysis. Using

different concentrations of the two salts in solution, the titrations were performed both by the direct and the inverse methods [*i.e.*, when $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ was added from the microburette to $NiSO_4$ in the titration cell and *vice-versa*]. Potassium ferrocyanide solution containing 1% potassium ferricyanide was used to make ferri-ferrocyanide electrode (Kolkhoff and Furman, 'Potentiometric Titrations', New York, 1947, p. 323). A platinised platinum foil was used as an indicator electrode in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. The E.M.F. was measured on a Cambridge p_H -meter. The titrations were also carried out in presence of alcohol up to a total concentration of 20% by volume. Curves were plotted between the volume of the titre and the E observed and from the sharp jump in potential, indicated by the titration curves, the end-point could be found out; this was further checked by calculating the maximum value of $\Delta E/\Delta C$ in each case. The reagent (20 c.c.) was taken in the electrode vessel each time. For the sake of brevity only two figures have been given, one for the direct and the other for reverse titrations.

TABLE I

Summary of results of potentiometric titrations.

$K_4Fe(CN)_6$	$NiSO_4$	Calc.	Points of equivalence required for the formation of $4Ni_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3K_4Fe(CN)_6$ observed from $\Delta E/\Delta C$ in presence of		
			0% alcohol.	10% alcohol.	20% alcohol.
			Direct titrations.		
M/5	M/20(20 c.c.)	4.375 c.c.	4.20 c.c.	4.30 c.c.	4.35 c.c.
M/20	M/100 (,,)	3.50	3.40	3.45	3.57
			Reverse titrations.		
M/20(20 c.c.)	M/5	5.70 c.c.	5.80	5.75	5.70
M/100 (,,)	M/20	4.57	4.70	4.60	4.55

DISCUSSION

From the strength of solutions of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ (M/5 and $NiSO_4$ M/20) the calculated titre values for the formation of the more probable compounds are given below.

1. Titre values for 20 c.c. of M/20- $NiSO_4$ in direct titrations ...

$K_2NiFe(CN)_6$	$Ni_2Fe(CN)_6$	$4Ni_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3K_4Fe(CN)_6$
5.0 c.c.	2.5 c.c.	4.375 c.c.
[M/5- $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution]		
2. Titre values for 20 c.c. of M/20- $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in reverse titrations ...

5.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	5.71 c.c.
[M/5- $NiSO_4$ solution]		

The titre values required for the formation of the above compounds, employing different concentrations of reactants, can be calculated accordingly both in the direct and the reverse titrations.

It is clear from Figs. 1-2 and Table I that the reaction between $NiSO_4$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ can be successfully followed potentiometrically, applying ferri-ferrocyanide electrode with either of the substances used as the reagent. The point of inflection calculated from the maximum values of $\Delta E/\Delta C$ occurs at a stage where the molecular ratio of reactants,

$K_4Fe(CN)_6:NiSO_4$, is as 7:8 and corresponds to the formation of the compound $4Ni_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3K_2Fe(CN)_6$, and is much different from those required for the formation of other probable compounds, $K_2NiFe(CN)_6$ and $Ni_2Fe(CN)_6$, as reported earlier (*loc. cit.*).

FIG 1

Direct titration.

$M/4-K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to 20 c.c. $M/2-NiSO_4$ (c.c.).

FIG. 2

Reverse titration.

$M/5-NiSO_4$ added to 20 c.c. $M/2 K_4Fe(CN)_6$ (c.c.).

The titration curves have a regular shape, there is a sharp jump in potential at the end-point and the results are accurate and reproducible. In direct titrations, the potential does not remain steady in the beginning of the reaction, but assumes a steady value before the end-point; in the inverse titrations, however, the E.M.F. gradually rises from the beginning, potential becomes constant after each addition of the break and a sharp jump is observed at the end-point. In alcoholic solutions the break in potential is less than that in aqueous solution although the nature of titration curves remains unchanged in both cases.

It is evident from Table I that the observed titre values in direct titrations are slightly lower than the calculated points of equivalence in aqueous medium; while in

the case of reverse titrations, they are slightly higher. In the presence of increasing amounts of alcohol, the observed titre values in both cases gradually approach the calculated values more closely.

The discrepancy between the observed and the calculated titre values in aqueous medium and the subsequent change when the titrations are carried out in alcoholic medium, supports our views on the adsorptive and hydrolytic behaviour of such ferro- and ferricyanide complexes (cf. Saxena *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

In direct titrations, adsorption of Ni^{2+} ions by the precipitate would tend to lower the titre values in aqueous medium. In the reverse titrations, nickel ferrocyanide on hydrolysis would release some $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ ions which will consume some extra amount of NiSO_4 , howsoever little it may be, and hence, the amount of nickel sulphate required will be slightly greater than the calculated equivalent. Alcohol suppresses adsorption and hydrolysis, and hence, a closer approach to the theoretical values is envisaged by the experimental results. In presence of 20% alcohol, the observed titre values almost coincide with the calculated ones.

The results of potentiometric titrations suggest that nickel ferrocyanide is not a pure compound but is a double salt represented by the formula $4\text{Ni}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$. The formation of the double salt was also suggested by Tananaev and Levina by electrochemical methods (*loc. cit.*) and by Gasper (*loc. cit.*). There is no evidence of the formation of $\text{K}_2\text{NiFe}(\text{CN})_6$, as suggested by Treadwell and Chervet (*loc. cit.*).

Quantitative work on adsorption and hydrolysis in the case of nickel ferrocyanide is in progress and the results will be communicated shortly.

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